

Concept note – ADOPT IPM

Length of project: 48 months

Project period: 01 December 2022 – 30 November 2026

Project coordinator: Institut National de Recherche pour l’Agriculture, l’Alimentation et l’Environnement (INRAE), France

Consortium: 17 partners from six EU Member States (Belgium, Denmark, France, Italy, Netherlands, Spain), two from the United Kingdom, and 13 from China.

The project

ADOPT-IPM is an **EU-China joint action** set up by a total of 32 partners from EU Member States, as well as from China and the United Kingdom, including research institutes, universities, small enterprises and extension services. The project is funded under the Horizon Europe research and innovation framework programme for a period of four years (December 2022–November 2026). ADOPT-IPM aims to develop, optimise, and implement a range of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) tools and packages, and ultimately to reduce farmer dependency on conventional chemical pesticides in the EU Member States, China and associated countries.

The project is structured in **six work packages**: three research WPs, one WP for field demonstrations, one WP for dissemination and one WP for project management.

IPM tools to reduce the dependency on chemical pesticides

For many years, the **use of chemical pesticides** has been the primary method to reduce losses in agricultural production and secure food supply to a growing worldwide population. However, this widespread use has imposed risks to the environment, human health and non-target organisms. To address this, **environmentally sound and sustainable pest management methods**, such as biopesticides, have been developed. Their adoption by farmers via IPM has been promoted by the EU since 2009, as well as by China’s Ministry of Agriculture (MOA).

Nevertheless, the **adoption of IPM tools is slowed** by several **key barriers**. Indeed, many available non-chemical IPM tools:

1. have not been optimised and therefore lack reliability and/or effectiveness.
2. may not have been developed through integrated approaches, thus potentially being sub-optimal when combined in IPM packages.
3. are missing for key pests, notably new invasive pests or re-emerging pests.
4. lack demonstrations to farmers and dissemination to key stakeholders.

The project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 101060430.

Objectives and activities

The **ADOPT-IPM project will promote a global transition** to sustainable agricultural systems through the development, optimisation and implementation of IPM tools and packages, leading to a reduction in the dependency of farmers on chemical pesticides. The project is designed to simultaneously deliver the optimisation of existing IPM tools and the development of new ones. Furthermore, ADOPT-IPM aims to promote a rapid adoption by end users through optimised IPM packages, taking into consideration costs and benefits, environmental impact and sustainability. Together, the ADOPT-IPM partnership will:

- **Optimise existing IPM tools and practices** for key agricultural pests/diseases and weeds and evaluate them against end users' expectations, to overcome the constraints which currently limit their widespread use.
- **Develop new IPM tools** considering farmers' and agricultural businesses' priorities and legislation related issues.
- **Assess and demonstrate through field trials** selected IPM tools and packages under semi-field and commercial conditions, to measure the likely adoption of these IPM packages at farm level in the EU and China.
- **Disseminate knowledge to key stakeholders**, create a participatory framework that will ensure an ongoing dialogue among researchers, extension specialists and end users.
- **Support ADOPT-IPM SMEs** with the exploitation of IPM tools resulting from the project activities and the associated regulatory process.

ADOPT-IPM will **integrate relevant end users early in the research process** and involve farmers and other key stakeholders in the design and evaluation of experiments, to promote a bottom-up approach, ensure feedback from farmers and increase the potential uptake of IPM tools.

EU – China collaboration

Trade and other pathways have led to the globalisation of major pests on key crops. In light of these challenges, **EU and China have developed similar policy objectives** to reduce use of chemical pesticides through the development and implementation of IPM tools. Furthermore, China is the top world producer and exporter of various vegetables and fruits (e.g., tomato) that are consumed by both Chinese and EU citizens. A joint EU-China approach will enable agricultural products to be safer for consumers, while ensuring profitable trade among countries.

ADOPT-IPM will focus on four types of crops: tomato, leafy vegetables, maize and wheat. The choice of crops is based on their economic importance in the EU and China and their current pest management methods which rely largely on chemical pesticides. The experience and expertise of each region's partners will enable the consortium to efficiently adapt the IPM tools, practices and packages to address the specific problems faced by EU and Chinese farmers. For these four types of crops, the exchange of knowledge, practices and technologies will be of high value to the countries involved.

